

An Exploratory Study: Controversial Beliefs and Practices of Hijama Practitioners of Karachi, Pakistan

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Abstract:

Background: Cultural and spiritual beliefs have preserved the use of traditional practices, including al hijama (wet cupping), which is widely recognized for its purported therapeutic value and historical significance. Despite its popularity, the practice often lacks formal training and is frequently administered by unqualified practitioners, leading to false beliefs and potentially unsafe practices. **Objective:** To investigate the scientific knowledge and beliefs of hijama practitioners of Karachi, Pakistan, with a focus on identifying misconceptions, variations in practice, and the influence of cultural and religious beliefs on the practice of hijama therapy.

Methodology: A cross-sectional exploratory study was conducted involving 114 hijama practitioners from Karachi, who were recruited through various WhatsApp groups and enrolled in a seminar held in January 2023. The participants were required to complete a 37-item questionnaire covering their qualifications, practice methods, hygiene standards, and beliefs about the hijama therapy. Data were analyzed using spss version 20, employing mean, standard deviation, chi-square tests, and frequency distribution.

Results: Most participants (97.4%) were female, with only 39.5% possessing a license to practice. Many practitioners (89.5%) were motivated by the religious significance of hijama. The knowledge regarding the scientific theories and mechanism of action of hijama therapy was known by 56.4%. Practices varied widely regarding hygiene, blade type, and cup placement. 38.1% did not consistently check for infectious diseases. Additionally, the practice of reciting Qur'anic verses was widespread, believed to enhance the therapy's effectiveness which shows strong religious connotation.

Conclusion: The study reveals a substantial gap in formal training among hijama practitioners, leading to variations in practice and potential safety concerns. There is a pressing need for standardized training and regulations to ensure the safe and effective practice of hijama therapy. Further research is essential to establish evidence-based guidelines which improve the public and physician awareness towards this therapy's risks and benefits.

Keywords: *Hijama practitioners, controversial beliefs, hijama practices.*

Introduction

Cultural and spiritual beliefs have sustained traditional practices since ancient times due to their perceived explanatory power (National Center for Complementary and Alternative Medicine, n.d.; Tangkiatkumjai, Boardman, & Walker, 2020). Al hijama, or wet cupping therapy, is one such practice deeply rooted in Islamic tradition (Ibn Razali, & Kartika, 2021; Qureshi, et al., 2017; Saif, & Siddiqui, 2022). This therapy involves placing cups on the skin to create suction and then drawing blood from superficial incisions, believed to enhance healing by improving blood circulation and eliminating toxins (Qureshi, et al., 2017; Saif, & Siddiqui, 2022; Niazi, et al., 2023; Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020).

Despite its growing recognition of its scientific evidence and therapeutic benefits (Niazi, et al., 2023; Aboushanab, & Alsanad, 2018; Al-Bedah, et al., 2019; Hani, & Saleem, 2019; Allafi, & Al-Haifi, 2020; Kaya, Tasdemir, & Cayır, 2022) especially among Muslims, wet cupping remains controversial and is often labeled as pseudoscience by healthcare professionals (Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020; El-Olemy, et al., 2017; Amber, Nini, & Zulfiqar, 2024). This skepticism stems from various factors, including the lack of clear mechanisms of action (Amber, Nini, & Zulfiqar, 2024), inadequate knowledge among hijama practitioners (National Center for Complementary and Alternative Medicine, n.d.; Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020; El-Olemy, et al., 2017), lack of awareness among conventional health care practitioners (Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020; El-Olemy, et al., 2017; Amber, Nini, & Zulfiqar, 2024; Iktidar, et al., 2022; Al Zaabi, et al., 2023) and the absence of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) integration into the mainstream medical education (Iktidar, et al., 2022; Al Zaabi, et al., 2023).

Although many health care bodies are struggling towards the regulation of hijama therapy in their region, unfortunately no universal hijama

training program is registered globally (Khalil, et al., 2018; Sajid, 2016; Mayberry, 2018), which contributes to the persistence of false beliefs and misconceptions. This fact is often perpetuated by unqualified practitioners and traditional healers who view minimal training as sufficient for its practice (Omar, & Alaban, 2022). Some even claim that a single hijama point can cure all diseases (Ghods, Sayfour, & Ayati, 2016). A study conducted in Saudi Arabia (El-Olemy, et al., 2017) revealed significant variations in practitioners' beliefs before hijama training, including gaps in baseline knowledge, hygiene practices, procedural techniques, and blade selection however, these misconceptions were largely corrected after training (El-Olemy, et al., 2017) which emphasize the need for training.

Rationale

In Pakistan, there is a growing movement to formalize training programs, establish certification processes, and develop evidence-based guidelines to ensure that hijama is practiced safely and effectively. Additionally, awareness among public (Khan, 2021) and health care workers (Amber, Nini, & Zulfiqar, 2024; Razzaq, Khan, & Zehra, 2013) is increasing steadily so it is crucial to correct the false beliefs and practices, particularly given the religious significance associated with this therapy. This study aims to reduce the incidence of malpractice, adverse effects, and complications and chance to avail this practice only with proper licence and training.

Objectives

To investigate the beliefs and practices of hijama practitioners of Karachi, Pakistan, with a focus on identifying misconceptions, variations in practice, and the influence of cultural and religious beliefs on the practice of hijama therapy.

Materials and Methodology

Study Design and Setting

To conduct this cross-sectional study, hijama practitioners of Karachi, Pakistan, were contacted through different WhatsApp groups for a seminar with the theme "Practice hijama after proper training". This seminar was organized in collaboration with the Pakistan professional hijama society in January 2023. Practitioners were asked to complete a questionnaire about their hijama practices before attending the seminar.

Inclusion Criteria

All identified individuals actively practicing hijama in the Karachi region were eligible to participate.

Exclusion criteria

Practitioners were excluded if they did not submit their complete questionnaires prior to the seminar.

Data Collection and Questionnaire

The primary author provided participants with a pre-designed questionnaire comprising 37 questions in a word document format made by the primary author herself. Participants were asked to complete the questionnaire after the details were explained to them, ensuring full comprehension. The questionnaire covered a range of topics, including the participants' basic qualifications, licensing status, the duration and location of their hijama practice, and the variety of diseases they have treated.

To assess the practitioners' knowledge, the questionnaire included specific questions aimed at determining whether hijama therapists could differentiate between hijama blood and normal venous blood. It also inquired about their ability to evaluate a patient's internal condition based on skin changes and blood type, as well as their understanding of lunar dates. The survey also explored the practitioners' practices, including how they take patient histories, check vital signs, and consider contraindications (especially for blood-borne diseases). Additionally, it addressed

pre- and post-hijama care, hygiene standards and precautionary measures, the recitation of prayers, cupping techniques, and the use of cupping equipment.

Data Management and Analysis

The collected data were entered into a computer system, where it was cleaned and analyzed using the spss statistical software package for windows, version 20. For quantitative data, the mean, standard deviation (SD), and analysis of variance (anova) were utilized. Frequency distribution and percentages were calculated, and the chi-square test was used to analyze qualitative, categorical data. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration

All participants were thoroughly briefed on the aims and objectives of the study. Any questions or concerns raised by individual participants were addressed promptly. They were assured that the study posed no risks and that their responses and records would remain confidential. Participation in the study and completion of the questionnaire were considered as providing informed consent.

Results

In this study, 114 participants completed the study form. The majority were females, making up 97.4% of the sample. The basic educational status of the participants was 18% have basic 10th grade, 11%.6% were homeopathic doctors, 5 % were conventional doctors, 5% have master's degree other than medicine and 4% practitioners have herbal medicine degree.

Among all practitioners 44.7 % were practicing only hijama therapy, 20.2% practice herbal medicine, 16.7 % practice homeopathy, 14.9 % complement it with spiritual healing, 21.9 % with mental counselling, 8.8% practice hijama with allopathy, 7 % practice reiki healing, 8.8 % acupressure and acupuncture, and 7 % did physiotherapy in conjunction with hijama therapy.

Table 1. Assessing the License Status and Practices of Hijama Practitioners

		Frequency	%
Do you have a license/degree to practice hijama therapy?	Yes	45	39.5
	No	69	60.5
If you don't have a license, where did you get your training from? Choose n/a if you have a license.	N/a	11	9.6
	Not sure about the qualification of my trainer	3	2.6
	Licensed hijama practitioner	40	35.1
	Doctor	27	23.7
	Unlicensed but experienced hijama practitioner	30	26.3
On average, how many patients do you treat per month?	0-10	67	58.8
	10-20	26	22.8
	20-30	10	8.8
	30-40	2	1.8
	40-50	4	3.5
	More than 50	4	3.5
Do you read research articles related to hijama?	Regularly	31	27.2
	Sometimes	75	65.8
	Rarely or never	8	7.0
Do you maintain your patients' records?	Always	83	72.8
	Sometimes	28	24.6
	Never	3	2.6
Do you take patients' medical history before hijama?	Always	109	95.6
	Sometimes	5	4.4
Do you take patients' surgical history before hijama?	Always	110	96.5
	Sometimes	3	2.6
	Never	1	.9
Do you take ladies menstrual history before hijama?	Always	106	93.0
	Sometimes	6	5.3
	Never	2	1.8
Do you check patients' blood pressure before hijama?	Always	37	32.5
	Sometimes	39	34.2
	Never	13	11.4
	Only of specific patients	25	21.9
Do you check blood sugar level of your patients before hijama?	Only symptomatic patients	21	18.4
	Only diabetic patients	61	53.5
	Each and every patient	5	4.4
	I don't check blood sugar level	27	23.7
Do you inform patients about the benefits and side effects of hijama before doing it?	Always	77	67.5
	Sometimes	9	7.9
	Never	1	.9
	Only when they ask	5	4.4
	Depends on time	1	.9
	Only in first visit	21	18.4
Do you inform patients about the procedure before doing it?	Always	74	64.9
	Sometimes	13	11.4
	Never	4	3.5
	Only when they ask	20	17.5
	I do not practice this therapy under supervision	18	15.8
Do you practice hijama under some supervision?	I always practice under a doctor's supervision	17	14.9
	I always practice under a licensed hijama practitioner's supervision	36	31.6

	I do not practice under constant supervision, but I consult with a doctor for any guide that I need	16	14.0
	I do not practice under constant supervision, but I consult with a licensed hijama practitioner for any guide that I need	25	21.9

When asked about their reasons for choosing hijama therapy, 89.5% cited its religious background as the primary motivation. Additionally, 63.2% were drawn to the therapy because they had observed its effectiveness in treating various illnesses, 51.8% wanted to improve the health of their family members, and 7.9% chose it as a means of earning an income.

Regarding the practice location, out of the 114 respondents, 42.1% practiced at their own homes, 50.9% practiced in a clinic or specific healthcare center, and 5.3% provided the

therapy at their clients' homes. A small percentage, 1.8%, fell into another unspecified category. Most of them, around 85%, get their clients from friends or relatives and from their old clients and only 9 % advertise via media to promote their client age.

Underlying mechanism of action and scientific knowledge of hijama was well known by 56.4%, 30% have moderate knowledge and 12 % knows little about it.

Figure 1. shows the practitioner knowledge about the contraindication of hijama therapy.

Figure 1. The Practitioner Knowledge about the Contraindication of Hijama Therapy

Regarding the perceived beneficial roles of hijama therapy across various health areas, a significant majority (90.9%) believe that hijama is beneficial for muscles, bones, and joints. This

is closely followed by its perceived benefits in the gastrointestinal and endocrine systems (85.5%) as shown in figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Perceived Beneficial Role of Hijama in Various Areas

Knowledge about the fasting duration required before hijama shows that 94.5% of practitioners believe fasting for 2 to 4 hours is necessary. Another misconception that emerged is the belief that hijama is a cure for all diseases, with 81% agreeing with this statement, while only 11% disagreed. Additionally, 41% of practitioners believe that hijama therapy can worsen some diseases, 26% are unsure, and 30% believe it does not worsen the symptoms of any disease. Regarding side effects, 41% of practitioners believe there are none, while 29% think hijama therapy does have side effects. When asked about the difference between venous blood and hijama blood, 87% recognized that they are different, while 13% did not.

Concerning the spread of infectious diseases through hijama, 48% of practitioners believe it cannot spread infections, 14% are unsure, and 30% agree that hijama therapy can transmit infectious diseases from the patient to the therapist. Regarding blood tests for infectious diseases, the majority (34.2%) reported not having their blood checked. This is followed by 17.5% who get tested once a year, 39% who

always check the patient's blood before hijama, 26.4% who only check when they feel suspicious, and 30% who ask patients about infectious diseases but do not check blood reports.

When asked about the effectiveness of hijama on specific lunar dates, 79% agreed that hijama is more effective during these times, while 18% disagreed. The majority (90.4%) believed there is no specific season for hijama therapy. Regarding preferred days for performing hijama, 67.5% of respondents expressed no preference for specific days, and 69.3% stated that any time is suitable.

The duration of cup placement before making an incision varies among practitioners: 29% keep the cup in place for 5 to 10 minutes, 32% adjust the timing based on the location and the patient's condition, and 25% place the cups for less than 5 minutes. After making the laceration, 44.9% reapply the cups until blood stops coming out, 55% said it depends on the location and blood quantity, 14% remove the cup when the blood

starts to clot, and 11% remove the cup after 5 minutes, as measured by a clock.

Regarding the choice of cups, 73.7% of practitioners use both glass and plastic cups. Most participants prefer using plastic gloves (44.7%), followed closely by latex/surgical gloves (43.9%). A significant majority (94.7%) change gloves for every patient. As for blades, the common razor blade is preferred by most (76.3%), and nearly all participants (99.1%) change their blades for each patient.

In terms of safety measures during hijama therapy, the most observed precaution is wearing gloves, with 99.1% of participants adhering to this practice. Using sterilized or new equipment is also widely followed, with 88.2% implementing this measure. Additionally, 76.4% of practitioners stay with the patient throughout the procedure, while 55.5% wear masks and 53.6% wear head cover for added protection.

Regarding the recitation of Qur'anic verses, 90.9% of respondents reported doing so, believing it plays a significant role in healing both the body and mind. In this study, 72.7% of participants felt that it protects patients from evil influences, 75.5% believed it enhances the effectiveness of hijama therapy, and 78% thought it shields the therapist from the negative energies of their clients. On the other hand, 9.1% stated that reciting the Quran is not necessary, 2.7% were unsure, and 0.9% believed it has no role in the process.

During the procedure, 73.6% of participants consider noting the blood color important, 67.3% focus on the amount of blood in the hijama cups, 64.5% observe blood consistency, 70.9% notice skin changes, and 56.4% look for fumes in the cupped blood. Physical changes in the patient are noted by 62.7%, and 46.4% monitor the pain threshold.

After the procedure, 49.1% of therapists apply antiseptic to the cupping site, 15.5% wash it with normal saline, and 66.5% apply oil after cleaning with tissue paper. Honey is applied by 39.1%, while 22.7% simply clean with tissue paper. Dressing or wet wipes are rarely used (0.9%).

For cup disposal, 45.5% of practitioners break and trash them, 34% ask clients to do the same, and a small number burn or reuse them. Regarding bandaging the cupping site, 87.2% leave the wound open, while 12.8% apply dressing.

For post-hijama care, 69.1% of practitioners provide specific instructions about bathing, 53.6% advise on wound care, and 39.1% recommend applying antiseptic. Dietary restrictions are advised by 65.5%, 27.3% suggest exercise, and 35.5% inform patients about potential body changes within the first 24 hours, such as pain, body aches, fever, vomiting, diarrhea, or sleep disturbances. Only 3% of practitioners provide no advice to their patients

Discussion

Hijama therapy has a long history of practice in Pakistan, but only come into notice for two decades, yet there is a notable lack of data regarding the knowledge, beliefs, and practices of those who perform it, this study, conducted in Karachi, Pakistan is the first to explore these elements in detail. The practitioners surveyed come from a wide range of educational backgrounds, with only 20% having a medical education, mostly in homeopath and a mere 5% being allopathic doctors. Notably, 60.5% of practitioners operate without a license, having received training from traditional healers who, despite their experience, lack formal certification. Their practice is largely unsupervised, motivated by observed therapeutic benefits and the religious significance of the therapy. This is consistent with findings from similar studies in Saudi Arabia by Khalil et al. (2018), Khawla et al., (2020), UAE by Alzabi et al., (2023) and Bangladesh by Iktidar et al., (2022) where many hijama practitioners also lack formal medical training and operate without licenses, guided by traditional and religious motivations.

Worldwide cupping therapy is regarded as complementary alternative therapy, and it should be combined alongside other therapies to provide a more holistic approach¹. In the current

study, it was observed that only 44% of individuals practice hijama therapy as a solo therapy. However, the remaining participants combine it with other forms of CAM, such as herbal therapy, homeopathy, spiritual healing, or massage therapy.

Practitioners in this study often favor hijama for its perceived effectiveness, particularly in treating musculoskeletal pain, gastrointestinal issues, and dermatological conditions consistent with previous researches, where they have shown the effectiveness of hijama therapy in multiple diseases focus mainly on musculoskeletal problems (Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020; Hssanien, et al., 2017; Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018) than the other conditions like in mental health, headache and dermatological condition (Qureshi, et al., 2017; Niazi, et al., 2023; Kouser, et al., 2021; Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020; Ghods, Sayfour, & Ayati, 2016).

A comprehensive review conducted by Albedah et al. in 2019, six potential mechanisms for hijama effects were identified. In current study 50% of the practitioners, demonstrate a solid understanding of the scientific mechanisms behind cupping therapy, and 30% are actively engaged in continuing education by reading new research consistent with Saudi study where practitioner exhibited good knowledge (Khan, 2021). Additionally, the knowledge mentioned in previous studies (Niazi, et al, 2023; Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020; Khan, 2021; Siddiqui, Shoaib, & Sultana, 2024; Jadhav, 2018; Hijamah in the light of Sharia and empirical science, n.d.) that hijama blood is distinct from venous blood and contains more toxins persisted with current study.

While history taking is an essential component before hijama procedure as mentioned in some studies (Hijamah (cupping therapy) for pain management in patients with cervical spondylosis, 2023; Salah, 2023), some practitioners may overlook it, leading to complications, shown by a study when treating cases of cervical spondylosis (Abbas Zaidi, et al., 2016) during hijama therapy. Thus, integrating thorough assessments into hijama practice is

vital for safe and effective practice. Fortunately, in current study many practitioners maintain patient records, take thorough medical histories, and inquire about contraindications before performing hijama, while there is considerable inconsistency in practices such as monitoring vital signs. For example, only 32.5% of practitioners consistently check blood pressure before treatment. This variability in patient care practices aligns with findings from other studies by Khalil et al in Saudi Arabia, Saad et al from Egypt, which also report a wide range of approaches among practitioners. To practice cupping therapy safely, a quality model for selecting patients has been developed in Saudi Arabia for the standardization and safety of treatment methods. where practitioners will not allow to start cupping therapy until they take the patient history, vital sign, asking for contraindication and took informed consent (Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018).

One study emphasizes the importance of blood test before hijama therapy which includes assessing viral hepatitis status, ferritin levels, and overall health to optimize treatment outcomes and ensure safety and efficacy (Hijamah (cupping therapy) for pain management in patients with cervical spondylosis, 2023). Other study emphasizes the importance of assessing blood sugar levels, bleeding and clotting times, anticoagulant therapy history, and advising post-therapy rest and dietary precaution (Salah, 2023). In current study, although the practitioners did not mention the specific test asked but they had given post therapy advice.

Skin changes after cupping is one of the main characteristics of cupping therapy (CT) and are used in diagnosing the internal condition of the patient in oriental medicine .There are many researches done in this field to analyze or explain these marks as diagnostic (Qureshi, Al-Baddah, & Aboushanab, 2017; Kim, & Lee, 2014; Zhao, et al., 2009) the color of the marks may vary, ranging from light red or pink to dark purple, depending on the individual's skin type and the treatment's intensity (Moura, et al., 2018). Many practitioners in this study also emphasize the significance of hijama blood's color and

consistency and consider the skin discoloration as an important observation.

A common belief, shared by 48.3% of participants in a Saudi study, is that the "Alkahel" Area on the back is used for treating all diseases through cupping, a practice also mentioned by several traditional writers (Ghods et al, al Bedah et al) this concept is consistent with current study in which 81 % of the practitioners posing same belief and they called this point as sunnah point (Benli, & Sunay, 2017). The significance of this point as sunnah point is mentioned in authentic Nabawi books, that-it is one of the spots on the body where the prophet Muhammad (ﷺ) received cupping (sahih al-Bukhari 5701; sahih Muslim 1203 Sunan Abu Dawood 3860. In traditional Islamic medicine, the al-kaheil area refers to the upper part of the back, between the shoulders, or the base of the neck and considered a vital point for removing stagnant blood and treating various ailments, especially headaches, neck pain, and issues related to blood circulation. The evidence shows that this point is employed in cupping techniques to lessen myofascial pain by removing the metabolic wastes that generate pain, lactic acid, interstitial fluid, and the causative pathological substance (CPS). (Setyawan, et al., 2022). In one of the studies in Iran only this point is used to treat mental health of the patients⁴¹. Other review articles show these autologous healing substances in a specific area, stimulating metabolic activity, improving immune function, and stabilizing blood biochemistry (Kordafshari, et al., 2017).

Another significant finding is the preference for performing hijama during specific lunar phases and days of the week, noted by 79% of practitioners. The prophet (ﷺ) said: "The best day to have cupping done is the 17th, 19th, or the 21st of the lunar month." (Sunan Abu Dawood 3861; the prophet (ﷺ) said: "Whoever wants to perform hijama (cupping), then let him search for the 17th, 19th, or 21st of the lunar month (Sunan ibn Majah 3486) according to the lunar motion theory, as the moon descends, gravitational effects cause blood to accumulate in certain areas of the human body and performing hijama therapy during these specific

lunar phases is believed to help treat various diseases more effectively by targeting these points one study done in Saudi Arabia highlights the potential differences in cupping therapy's efficacy on vital signs between sunnah and non-sunnah dates (Syahruramdhani, Risdiana, & Setyawan, 2021) and another done on migraine with the underlying facts that the moon phase can affect the heart's performance, blood flow, and the human hormonal system (Benli, & Sunay, 2017).

This study highlights the significance of incorporating religious practices, such as Qur'anic recitations, during hijama therapy. These practices reflect the cultural and spiritual roots of hijama in Pakistani society and are believed to enhance the treatment's effectiveness. They think that according to hadith (Sahih Bukhari 5742), reciting Qur'anic verses during treatment helps heal illness and remove negative influences, enhancing both the patient's and practitioner's well-being. But acc. to the correct jurisprudential of Islam, this is not supported by strong evidence in hadith science. As hadiths mentioned to support reading roqia, reading Al Korsi Aya or certain doa during hijama, these hadiths vary from fake to weak evidence. So, we cannot rely upon them (Hijamah in the light of Sharia and empirical science, n.d.).

In previous studies hijama practitioners believe that hijama is a safe practice without any side effects (Aboushanab, & Alsanad, 2018; Khan, 2021; Razzaq, Khan, & Zehra, 2013; Hssanien, et al., 2017; Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018). In current studies, while most believe that hijama is free of adverse effects, 48% of the practitioners believe that hijama has side effects indicating that 93 % believe hijama has no side effects and only 7% of participants experienced adverse effects (Al-Luhaidan, & Prarthana, 2020). While other review article on cupping therapy shows that cupping therapy had local reaction like ecchymosis, bruises, blister formation (Jadhav, 2018) burns and vasovagal syncope in some patient (National Center for Complementary and Alternative Medicine, n.d.; Niazi, et al., 2023; Ghods, Sayfour, & Ayati, 2016; Furhad, Sina, & Bokhari, 2023). But these reactions are usually

very mild and bear able by patient with counselling and mostly seem to be physiological.

While most practitioners (94.7%) adhere to basic hygiene practices like changing gloves for every patient and using separate cups and blades for each patient, gaps remain in other safety measures this might be consistent with the researches (Khan, 2021) where one even assume that hijama can cause septic arthritis (Kim, & Kang, 2015) and the other express the idea that hijama therapy increases the risk of blood borne infection (Rehman et al., (2014). In the current study only a minority of practitioners regularly check blood for infectious diseases, both themselves and their clients and only 34 % agreed that hijama therapy transmits blood born disease. So, care must be taken to change gloves and use separate equipment for each patient (Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018).

Researchers recommend that cups should be left on the skin for a maximum of 5 to 10 minutes during a cupping therapy session (Niazi, et al., 2023; Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018; Furhad, Sina, & Bokhari, 2023). This duration is deemed adequate to attain the intended therapeutic effects without causing unnecessary discomfort or adverse reactions. In the current study variable practices were found among practitioners regarding duration of cup placement.

Additionally, the study points to a lack of uniformity in practices related to cup selection, disposal of used equipment, and post-hijama care. Similar issues were observed in a Saudi study (El-Olemy, et al., 2017), where many practitioners believed that sterilizing cups was unnecessary, although such beliefs improved after training. In Korea for single-use, disposable cupping cups are recommended to minimize infection risks in cupping therapy supported by government policies in korea (Kim, & Kang, 2015).

Although previous studies are comparable to the current study, differences emerge in the extent of regulation and standardization. In countries with more robust healthcare systems, such as Europe (Sajid, 2016), the UAE (Al Zaabi, et al., 2023), and Saudi Arabia (Khalil, et al., 2018;

Sajid, 2016; Aboushanab, & AlSanad, 2018), efforts to regulate hijama practice have included formal training programs and licensing requirements. In contrast, the current study highlights the lack of regulatory frameworks in Pakistan, which contributes to the inconsistent practices observed among practitioners. This underscores the need for improved regulation and standardization to ensure the safe and effective practice of hijama therapy.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concludes that hijama therapy in Karachi is widely practiced without standardized training or regulation, leading to significant variations in practitioner knowledge, beliefs and practices, which may compromise patient safety. To ensure the safe and effective practice of hijama therapy, it is essential to establish comprehensive training programs and certification processes that equip practitioners with the necessary skills and knowledge. Implementing standardized hygiene protocols is crucial to minimizing the risk of blood born infections, thereby safeguarding both practitioners and clients. Additionally, developing evidence-based clinical guidelines, informed by rigorous scientific research, will provide a solid foundation for best practices in hijama therapy. Public awareness campaigns are also vital, as they can educate both practitioners and the public about the scientifically supported benefits and potential making.

Limitation

This study focuses only on a small group of hijama practitioners who are willing to share their knowledge and enroll in a seminar to learn more about this therapy. This represents just the tip of the iceberg, as the actual number of practitioners and their methods remain largely unknown and unexamined.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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